

<https://ijlmss.com/>

ISSN (2790-976X)

Effective Leadership Style on Jobs Satisfaction

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾**Rabia Musa**

Email: Rabiamusa12@gmail.com

Shaheed Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto Institute of Science and Technology (SZABIST), Islamabad.

⁽²⁾**Irfan Ullah Khan**

Email: Ifraan16@gmail.com

Shaheed Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto Institute of Science and Technology (SZABIST), Islamabad.

⁽³⁾**Nadeem Ehsan**

Email: m4nadeem@yahoo.com

Center for Advanced Studies in Engineering (CASE), Islamabad

Abstract

The development of effective leadership style is a major concern for most of the organization and so in academia. The focus of current study is to see whether servant leaders are satisfied with their jobs or not basically to see how servant leadership effect on job satisfaction in academia and whether organization environment moderates positively or negatively the relationship of independent and dependent variable. Data is collected from the 250 faculty like Professors, Assistant Professors and Lecturers both male and female working in the private six universities but got back 215 questionnaires. Data is collected through a questionnaire. Hypotheses were developed to see the impact of servant leadership on job satisfaction. To shows that servant leadership has significant effect on job satisfaction whereas second shows that organization positively moderates the relationship of independent and dependent variable and it's proved through statistical mean.

Keywords: *Servant leaders, Job Satisfaction, Faculty, Private Universities and Organization Environment.*

Introduction

Human Resource Management is an important function in an organization which aims at the management of organizational workforce. In the light of human resource leadership in an organization aims at improving the performance of employees by giving them direction and motivating employees. Leadership has been an important factor in business world as it increases the efficiency and effectiveness of both employees and the organization when there is job satisfaction. The job satisfaction depends on various factors but leadership is one of the important factors for employee in order to have satisfaction with their jobs. Thus in organizations having a good leaders and dedicated employees one who are satisfy with his job determine into

long term profitability of an organization. In other words, job satisfaction is major factor or component for employee and organization performance.

As we know leadership has different forms such as transformational, transactional, authoritative, and participative and much more but my study revolves around servant leadership. Basic concern of this study is to maximize employee's performance through job satisfaction by linking it to servant leadership.

Crippen (2006) stated that servant leadership is defined as "first to serve, then to lead". As the term servant leadership indicates that the leader one who is a servant. Greenleaf's (1977) and Patterson (2003) theory supports to servant leadership and it is one who is inclined to serve rather than to lead. Their motive is to put forward other needs and other interests rather than looking for their own interests and organization goals. This how servant leadership is different style of leadership and I believe it is the appropriate style of leadership whose motive is to serve others. Thus focus of this study is to see servant leadership impact on job satisfaction.

As we all are aware of the fact that Academia plays a very important role in one's life as well as in economy of country. Thus they groom the students; they educate them, create awareness among the students and produces and develop an employee which than contribute to the economy of a country by different ways and this all happens due to the teachers, the true servant leaders.

This study is conducted in academia basically as teachers are the best servant leaders no one can be the best leaders as they are, they actually serve themselves for other's life. In this study we will come up with how much these servant leaders are dedicated to their job, how much they are satisfied with their jobs. The purpose of this research is to show the impact of servant leadership on job satisfaction in academic world.

Gap Analysis

The gap identified from the literature is that no one can be the good servant leader than a teacher where teachers actually produce and develop an employee; they actually groom the students that's why I conducted this study in Academia and as teachers are employee themselves in any institution so will see are they satisfy with their jobs or not and as not much of previously work is done in this regard (Zhang, Lin & Foo, 2012).

Secondly, will see the impact of servant leadership on job satisfaction with a moderator organization environment whether organization environment moderates the relationship of servant leadership and job satisfaction (Joseph & Winston, 2005).

Rationale of study

The rationale of this study is to show the impact of servant leadership on job satisfaction. Leadership is important to enhance the capabilities of employees in workplace and servant leadership is appropriate style in order to serve others. Study is conducted in academia as teachers are the best servant leaders but beside that they are employees as well in the respective institution so in this study we will see how much they are satisfy with their jobs, how much they are dedicated to their work.

Literature Review

Human resource is backbone and also the main discipline of any organization. Organizations invest huge amount on human resource because the performance of human resource will ultimately increase the performance of organization.

This section provides insights about earlier recognized details for servant leadership and its impact on job satisfaction with a moderating effect of organization environment. The discussion starts with certain key concepts and definitions pertaining to the area under study, which is job satisfaction as a dependent variable and organization environment as moderator. The discussion then highlights the theoretical reflections and substantiates the evidence from the literature related to the area under study; showing the linkages between independent, dependent and moderating variables. Furthermore, the study was aimed to find the relationship that exists between servant leadership and organizational performance; this portion endures by describing the critical analysis of literature, and it also describes the identified literature gap relating to the topic under study.

Job Satisfaction

Locke (1976, p. 1304) defined job satisfaction as “a pleasurable or emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one’s job or job experiences”. Gill (2008) proposed that job satisfaction can be improved in a way as it is important for managers/leaders to build employee trust. This is how; the employee would be more dedicated and satisfied in hospitality organization and will give their best.

Curtis and Wright (2001) mentioned that reason for leaving the organization is that managers/leaders are not providing or adopting appropriate leadership style or not valuing their employees/subordinates. Thus appropriate leadership is important in order to retain employees in an organization or in other words that style of leadership should be adopted which they think can be helpful for their employees in order to retain them which will increase their satisfaction level.

Employees should feel that their work, views or stance are being valued and appreciated. Their contributions to organization mean a lot to them. Valuing the employees suggestions or ideas not only raise the employee’s self-esteem but also going to higher their commitment towards the organization.

In order to motivate employees rewards both intrinsic and extrinsic play an important role. Extrinsic rewards include (promotion, pay) whereas intrinsic rewards such as appreciation and recognition. It is been supported by the research that both these types of rewards affects Outcomes such as retaining the employees in organization, their commitment to organization and job satisfaction (Tymon, Stumpf&Doh, 2010).

Gonzalez and Garazo (2006, p. 23) says leaders/managers in hotels should focus on front line employees to increase job satisfaction and their behavior should not be just towards organization but towards community as well. Therefore, service communicative leadership will influence employee’s loyalty not just to organization but to community and thus, this will improve the job satisfaction of employees as well.

It depends on the leader how they influence subordinates so that they can give best of them and this happens when management respect the employees, work with honesty, promote efficiency in order to be productive and provide open chance of communication (Aronson et al., 2003). Thus, two way communication is very important this make them feel valued and thus this boost up their confidence.

Job satisfaction would result in if there is opportunity of communication with the managers and team members. Thus, working in teams will result into cooperation which is best in order to improve job satisfaction (Zeffane & Mcloughlin, 2006). If working environment is good and comfortable than employees will be happier and will do their tasks with full dedication and commitment.

Management should promote open communication so that employees get to know about all the information this will strength the employees job satisfaction and their commitment towards their work (Rad & Yarmohammadin, 2006).

In services, good relationship and effective communication with management has developed team work and employees feel good working in teams this how they get support from their colleagues in team. Thus, this will make them happy and will satisfy too.

Servant Leadership

Greenleaf (1977) proposed the servant leadership model among modern organizational theorists, in this style of leadership the leaders solely work for their employees and make it a prime objective to serve and develop them. Crippen (2006) defined servant leadership by the slogan “first to serve, then to lead”. The detailed definition of servant leadership is “follower-centric, altruistic, moral/ethical and spiritual values” (Pekerti & Sendjaya, 2010).

As it is said “if one of you wants to be great, he must be servant of the rest; and if one of you wants to be first, he must be the slave of all”. So one who wants to be great he should be serving others rather than leading.

The motive of servant leadership is to meet other needs, to put forward others interests rather than own interests and valuing others by appreciating and praising them.

The concept of servant leadership has made a great change in the education leadership study by identifying the power. The shift in paradigm has been seen in this style of leadership from authority to empowerment approach (Dambe & Moorad, 2008). It's been seen that now trend is changing empowerment approach is adapted more rather than carrot-stick concept. People now want to work at their own, they want to work at their own this actually give them more strength. In other words the "true leadership emerges when one's primary motivation is to help others" (Hughes, Ginnett & Curphy, 2009, p. 187). One who is a leader he or she should not think in a way that they will control people, they should not be bossy at all they should inclined to serve others. Servant leadership is also referred as "supportive leadership" where the leader is "friendly and shows concerns for the needs of staff members (Robbins, 2005).

Zhang, Lin and Foo (2012) say servant leadership is most effective style of leadership than authoritative leadership because this style reflects better use of leader's power. This style is most effective because leaders in this style of leadership not use their power in a wrong way

This makes the employees more happy and satisfied. They not lead for sake of their interests Servant leaders are those whose primary concern is to serve their followers and thus this gives good image to the organization or institution. This style of leadership motive is to serve everyone who is associated with the organization (Hamilton & Bean, 2005). Servant leadership has power to motivate their leaders and followers and thus push them towards higher levels of morality.

Stone, Russell and Patterson (2004) stated that focus of servant leadership is on valuing the people in the organization rather than the organization itself. This is how this leadership is different from other leadership styles. Recognizing subordinates work, appreciating their efforts makes the employees satisfied and ultimately they get committed to their work thus, this will increase the productivity. Joseph and Winston (2005) state that leaders should be supportive enough and they should communicate with the employees as much as they can this will build trust among the employees and this is how employees will feel valued which will boost up the employee's confidence and their integrity will strengthen.

Anderson (2009) says showing concerns for others, giving importance to the needs of others and to their interests are the hallmarks of the servant leader and leaders with all these attributes will be preference of the employees/subordinates. The primary focus is to serve followers and to serve organization concerns is the secondary focus of servant leaders. Effective leadership is important for all sort of organization structure whether their involvement is in political, social or economic environment, both on large and small scale businesses, families and not formal groups (Galbraith & Schavaneveldt, 2005). Environment plays an important role and it's not matter what the environment is focus of consideration is to adapt best style of leadership in order to nurture and prosper.

Leaders are expected to give great attention to their employee's empowerment, their needs, and values and to serve the needs of the others (stewardship) in people-oriented culture (Dierendonck & Nuijten, 2010).

Oner (2012) said servant leadership is also associated with the emotions of employees. Servant leaders believe that it is their duty to see the overall personality of employees with whom they are associated. Their needs should be fulfilled at first, their interest should be their preference and it is expected out of them to create such environment in which the employees feel motivated to work and give their best out of it. Leaders actually become strength of the employees. It 'surge of servant leader to see their subordinates nurturing and reaching to their full potential.

Russell (2001) said that trust is the important element in any leadership style. Ultimately these values give them recognition by recognizing their efforts, by valuing their work to make them feel good. The core concept of servant leadership is based on the humility and respecting others.

Transformational leaders are different from servant leaders in a way transformational leaders are inclined to lead, their focus is on the needs of organization, preferring organization interests at first and influencing through charismatic approaches as well as through control whereas servant leaders are inclined to serve first and preferring employees interests and their needs at first (Parolini, 2007).

According to Ehrhart (2004) his servant leadership is different from transformational leadership in a way the focus of servant leaders is not only to achieve organization and personal goals but it's their responsibility to serve all those who are associated with the organization.

Servant leadership's first priority is to make service to the followers. The employees want pride and appreciation from their leaders i.e. intrinsic and this value more to them than extrinsic motivators (Parolini, 2009). Wisner et al., (2005) says employees' needs to feel that their skills and contributions are being valued. This is important at end of employees by doing so leaders are not just motivating employees but making them more dedicated towards their goals which they need to achieve.

Organization Environment

Bichard(2009) say such work environment should be created where employees get more chance to prove themselves. However this will be challenging for them and thus, they will pay all their attention to their work in order to meet those expectations. So working environment should be challenging where every other employee get chance to prove him and this how they will be treated fairly.

If environment is challenging employees will get more opportunities and thus, this will make them more enthusiastic towards their task or work given to them this how,they will perform the task with full dedication. They will bring innovation to their work; they will be able to contribute new ideas.

Kossek, Kalliath and Kalliath (2012) state that if working environment is healthy employees will be more satisfy with their jobs and they will perform their work without stress and will easily manage the work life and family life. If there is work life balance than things will be very easy to tackle and life will be very relax. If management is cooperating with employees giving respect to them, recognizing their efforts, appreciating their work this will results into healthy working environment which will ultimately increase the satisfaction level of employees. (Rad & Yarmohammadin, 2006).

Theoretical Framework

In my study servant leadership is the independent variable, job satisfaction is dependent variable and organization environment is a moderator.

Operational Definitions

- A. Servant leadership:** Leader must be valuing people, serving people and building relationship on trust (Greenleaf, 1977; Patterson, 2003).
- B. Job satisfaction:** Job satisfaction of faculty/leaders will be in terms of team work and communication (Rad & Yarmohammadian, 2006).
- C. Organization environment:** The key elements which strengthen the organization environment are challenges and healthy working environment (Bichard, 2009; Kossek, Kalliath & Kalliath 2012).

Hypotheses

On the basis of literature review and conceptual framework the following testable hypotheses are

H1: Servant leadership has significant effect on the job satisfaction.

H2: Organization environment has a positive effect on the relationship of servant leadership and job satisfaction.

Research Design

This is a cross sectional study conducted to explore the impact of servant leadership on job satisfaction. The significance of the relationship is explored on the survey based on primary data. It will also examine the relationship of organization environment as a moderating variable on the servant leadership and job satisfaction.

Data Collection method

Questionnaires based survey method was used for data collection. Questionnaire comprises of 22 questions and all questions were close ended using Likert scale.

Measurement

For the present study, a questionnaire was used to collect the data. I had adapted the questionnaire from the combination of studies. Study variables were measured by 5 point Likert scale where 1 was strongly agree and 5 was strongly disagree. Questionnaire consists of demographics (gender, designation, department and no. of years) and 22 items, of which 7 belonged to servant leadership (Drury, 2004; Beck, 2010), 9 to job satisfaction (Drury, 2004; Zeffane & McLoughlin, 2006) and 6 to organization environment (Drury, 2004).

Population

Researcher selected six private universities/institutions such as SZABIST, Muhammad Ali Jinnah, IQRA, University of Lahore, HITEC and FAST. My study focus was on the faculty like Professors, Assistant Professors and Lecturers both male and female in the respected institutions.

Sample and Sample size

The sample size of present study consisted of 250 faculty working in the private institutions and data was collected from Rawalpindi and Islamabad. The data was collected through questionnaires. All questionnaires were collected after 6 weeks and out of 250 responses I received back 215. The 215 questionnaires were included in the study. However, data was collected through faculty mainly professors, assistant professors and lecturers.

Reliability Analysis

	N of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Servant leadership	7	.632
Job satisfaction	9	.801
Organization environment	6	.789

Correlation

Pearson correlation with two tail level of significance was applied.

*. **Table 5: Correlation Matrix.**

	SL	JS	OE
Servant leadership	1		
Job satisfaction	.302**	1	
Organization environment	.452**	.427**	1

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Linear Regression analysis (servant leadership and job satisfaction)

Variable	B	SEB	t	B
H1 Servant leadership	.304	.064	4.782	.312
Constant	1.559	.154		

Note. R² = .097; F= 22.868, Durbin-Watson= 1.867

*p < .05

Test of moderation on Servant leadership – Job satisfaction Model (Moderator Organization environment)

Variable	B	SEB	t	B
H2 Organization Environment	.349	.067	5.199	.359
Constant	1.015	.179		

Note. R² = .200; F= 27.029,

*p < .05

Discussion

This study addresses two following questions: Is servant leadership effective for job satisfaction. Other question is whether organization environment moderates the relationship between servant leadership and job satisfaction? Few tests were conducted in order to respond these questions and statistical results indicate that servant leadership has significant effect on job satisfaction and organization environment positively moderates the relationship between independent and dependant variable.

This paper examines the influence of servant leadership with perspective of serving people, valuing people and building relationship on trust on job satisfaction with moderating effect of organization environment. All the results show that overall model developed for the research is significant. The significance of model shows that servant leadership has significant impact on job satisfaction and moderating variable was organization environment. In this study we have seen the significant effect of servant leadership on job satisfaction and thus, the effect was positive as p-value was less than .05% whereas organization environment has positively moderated the relationship of servant leadership and job satisfaction.

Thus, we can say that H1 was not rejected as it showed that servant leadership has positive effect on job satisfaction as sig. value was less than .05%. The second hypothesis in study was not rejected as well as organization environment has positively moderated the relationship because sig. value was less than .05% which means results are significant but model is valid because of the moderator, organization environment positively moderates the relationship between servant leadership and job satisfaction as R^2 was increased from 0.97 to .200. Thus, Durbin-Watson value was 1.867 which shows auto-correlation which is within acceptable range of 1.5-2.5. So, research questions conducted for this study is fully meaningful as both hypotheses are not rejected.

From the results it is found that servant leadership has significant effect on job satisfaction this shows one who is a servant leader if he or she is satisfied than he will be able to produce best; he will be able to perform his task with full dedication and commitment. Thus, this will make them more committed and loyal to their respective institutions and its of more importance that organization environment plays an important role because if organization environment is not strong, is not healthy enough people will get bored they will not be motivated at all which will ultimately result into poor performance, turnover will be high and this all will happen because of low satisfaction level.

Implications

Academic Implication

The study contributed to academia in a way that as we know no one can be the good servant leader than a teacher where teachers actually produce and develop an employee; they actually groom the students and importantly as teachers are employee themselves in any institution so will see are they satisfy with their jobs or not.

In this study dimensions took for servant leadership were three supported by the theory and moderator which was taken in this study was organization environment which was previously not taken in the studies.

Managerial Implications

The study contributed to management in a way that organizations have managers they can only manage the things but if they produce servant leaders they will serve employees and will meet their interests which will ultimately increase the productivity of organization.

The study focuses on very important aspect because if the leader is satisfied and is contented with his life they can serve others with more enthusiasm and optimism and by serving others needs in an organization they can easily motivate their employees which will increase the job satisfaction which ultimately lead to the productivity.

Furthermore, managers should be given training or workshops so that they can learn more about the servant leadership so that they can get to know the importance of this style of leadership.

Conclusion

Servant leadership has positive effect on job satisfaction in academia. As hypothesis H1: Servant leadership has significant effect on job satisfaction, H2: Organization environment has a positive effect on the relationship of servant leadership and job satisfaction. In the study H1 was not rejected so it has proved that servant leadership has significant impact on job satisfaction as it has been statistically proven and H2 was not rejected too because moderator has positively moderate the relationship. Thus, the development of effective leadership style is a major concern for most of the organization.

Recommendation

The issue should be investigated further in Pakistan's context again and below we are suggesting some of the future directions which one may follow in order to get significant results.

As sample size was limited so the sample should be increased to make study more detailed.

Future researchers should look for other moderating variables such as empowerment, organization justice and culture etc. and work can be done on public universities as well as this study was just limited to private universities in Islamabad and Rawalpindi and for future research more cities should also be included. Furthermore, current study is 1st stage study of servant leadership with its three dimensions such as serving people, valuing people and building relationship on trust. In future these three dimensions of servant leadership should be unfolded and should be studied in depth.

References

- i. Andersen, J. A. (2009). *When a servant-leader comes knocking... Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 30 (1), 4-15.
- ii. Aronson, K. R., Sieveking, N., Laurenceau, J. P., & Bellet, W. (2003). *Job satisfaction of psychiatric hospital employees: a new measure of an old concern. Administration and Policy in Mental Health*, 30 (5), 437-52.
- iii. Beck, C. D. (2010). *Antecedents of servant leadership: A mixed method study (Unpublished master's thesis, Nebraska University, Lincoln)*.
- iv. Bichard, E. (2009). *Creating a healthy work environment through sustainable practices. The Oxford Handbook of Organizational Well-Being*, 542.
- v. Crippen, C. (2006). *Servant-leadership. International Journal of Learning*, 13 (1), 13-18.
- vi. Curtis, S., & Wright, D. (2001). *Retaining Employees - The Fast Track to Commitment*. 24 (8).
- vii. Dambe, M., & Moorad, F. (2008). *From Power to Empowerment: A Paradigm Shift in Leadership. South African Journal of Higher Education*, 22 (3), 575-587.
- viii. Drury, S. (2004). *Employee Perceptions of Servant Leadership: Comparisons by Level and with Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment (Unpublished master's thesis, Regent University)*.
- ix. Ehrhart, M. G. (2004). *Leadership and procedural justice climate as antecedents of unit-level organizational citizenship behavior. Personnel Psychology*, 57 (1), 61-94.
- x. Galbraith, K. A., & Schvaneveldt, J. D. (2005). *Family leadership styles and Family Well-Being. Family and Consumer Sciences Research Journal*, 33 (3), 220-239.
- xi. Gill, A. S. (2008). *The role of trust in employee-manager relationship. International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 20(1), 98-103.
- xii. Gonzalez, J. V., & Garazo, T. G. (2006). *Structural relationships between organizational service orientation, contact employee job satisfaction and citizenship behavior. International Journal of Service Industry Management*, 17 (1), 23-50.
- xiii. Greenleaf, R. K. (1977). *Servant leadership: A journey into the nature of legitimate power and greatness*.
- xiv. Hamilton, F., & Bean, C. J. (2005). *The importance of context, beliefs and values in leadership development. Business Ethics A European Review*, 14 (4), 336-347.
- xv. Hughes, R., Ginnett, R., & Curphy, G. (2009). *Leadership: Enhancing the lessons of Experience*. 187.
- xvi. Joseph, E. E., & Winston, B. E. (2005). *A correlation of servant leadership, leader trust and organizational trust. Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, 26 (1), 6-22.
- xvii. Kossek, E. E., Kalliath, T., & Kalliath, P. (2012). *Achieving employee wellbeing in a changing work environment. International Journal of Manpower*, 33 (7), 73-753.

- xviii. Locke, E. A. (1976). *The nature and causes of job satisfaction. Handbook of Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, 1297-350.
- xix. Öner, Z. H. (2012). *Servant leadership and paternalistic leadership styles in the Turkish business context: A comparative empirical study. Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 33 (3), 300-316.
- xx. Patterson, K. (2003). *Servant leadership: a theoretical model.*
- xxi. Parolini, J. L. (2007). *Investigating the Distinctions Between Transformational and Servant Leaders.*
- xxii. Parolini, J., Patterson, K., & Winston, B. (2009). *Distinguishing between transformational and servant leadership. Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, 30 (3), 274-91.
- xxiii. Pekerti, A., & Sendjaya, S. (2010). *Exploring servant leadership across cultures: comparative study in Australia and Indonesia. The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 21 (5), 754-780.
- xxiv. Rad, A. M., & Yarmohammadian, M. H. (2006). *A study of relationship between managers' leadership style and employees' job satisfaction. Leadership in Health Services*, 19 (2).
- xxv. Robbins, S. P. (2005). *Organizational Behavior.*
- xxvi. Russell, R. F. (2001). *The role of values in servant leadership. Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 22 (2), 76-84.
- xxvii. Stone, A., Russell, R., & Patterson, K. (2004). *Transformational versus servant leadership: A difference in leader focus. Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, 25(4), 349-361.
- xxviii. Tymon, W. G., Stumpf, S. A., & Doh, J. P. (2010). *Exploring talent management in India: The neglected role of intrinsic rewards. Journal of World Business*, 45, 109-121.
- xxix. Dierendonck, V. D., & Nuijten, I. (2010). *The Servant leadership Survey (SLS): development and validation of a multidimensional measure. Journal of Business Psychology.*
- xxx. Wisner, P.S., Stringfellow, A., Youngdahal, W.E. & Parker, L. (2005). *The service volunteer-loyalty chain: an exploratory study of charitable not-for-profit service organizations. Journal of Operations Management*, Vol. 23 (2), 143-61.
- xxxi. Zeffane, R. & McLoughlin, D. (2006). *Exploring the differentials impact of job satisfaction, communication and culture. Management Research News*, Vol. 29 (10), 618-631.
- xxxii. Zhang, Y., Lin, T.B. & Foo, S. F. (2012). *Servant leadership: a preferred. Chinese Management Studies*, 6 (2), 369-383.